

A MULTI-DISCIPLINARY APPROACH TO THE STUDY OF AN ASSEMBLAGE OF COPPER BASED FINDS ASSIGNED TO THE PREHISTORY AND PROTO-HISTORY OF FUCINO, ABRUZZO, ITALY

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The project aims to characterize, by a corpus of archaeometric analyses, an assemblage of copper-based finds known as 'Fucino bronzes', most of which lacking of any finding data.

The complex of Fucino bronzes include bronzes emerged during the Fucino lake drainage, at the end of the XIX century, and bronzes locally bought or dug after that by a number of collectors on behalf of various Italian museums, where finds are currently dispersed.

Study develops exploring firstly dynamics related to the objects production and assemblage and secondly relationships among production centres, local workshops and the emergence of iron.

Research will extend analysis to finds from recent digs as bronzes, vitrified material, smelting or casting pottery.

This study proceeds contemporary on various research and cataloguing phases:

- quantification
- chemical analysis
- macro and micro-metallographic examination
- drawing up of a database

For this research, finds are functionally grouped in three main categories: 1) ornaments and accessories, 2) instruments and 3) weapons, but, at the same time, quantification is unrolling by grouping finds also chronologically, typologically, technologically and, when possible, territorially in order to build custom models for interpretation of data.

In this memory we report quantification, chemical analysis and metallography of selections of materials, as "Kardiophylakes", as an example, bronze or bronze/iron disks with about one-third of the known samples in this assemblage, 38 of which reporting provenience from specific Fucino sites.

Chemical analyses are carried on by the portable ED-XRF which provides quantitative results comparable with data of similar bronze characterization projects as the San Francesco hoard in Bologna and the Chieti Archaeological Museum.

Macro metallographic analysis of finds will be carried on by optical microscope (OM) and SEM.